

Comparative Study of Conventional and Certificate of Occupancy Redefined Methods of Land Title Registration in Oyo State

Olukotun, S.A¹ and Adediran, A².

^{1&2}Department of Built Environment, Lead City University, Ibadan.

ajayiolukotun19@gmail.com

Abstract

This study compared the conventional and certificate of occupancy methods of registration of ownership in Oyo state, Nigeria. Primary and secondary data were used for the study. Two sets of interview guides were administered to elicit relevant information for the study. Purposive sampling procedure was used in the selection of the beneficiaries of the programme. 1000 interview guides were administered to elicit primary data such as efficiency of C of O redefined in term of procedure, cost and time compared to the conventional approach. However, 800 interview guides were retrieved for final analysis. The primary data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics including mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square, at $p \leq 0.05$, respectively. A 4-point Likert scale was used in scaling the responses of the participants in the study. The respondents are generalized to agree to an item on the questionnaire and the chosen level of significance is 5%. The result of the hypothesis test on efficiency of time, procedure and cost showed that C of O redefined methodology is more efficient than the conventional method. The Chi-square value was highly significant (.000) which was less than the chosen level of significance. The Null hypothesis was rejected since P-value .000 was less than the chosen level of significance. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis which states that conventional approach is less efficient than Certificate of Occupancy redefined methodology is accepted.

Keywords: Conventional Method; Certificate of Occupancy; Redefined Method; Land Titling and Registration

1.1 Background to the Study

Largely due to poverty, 70% of the World Population lacks title to their property (World

Bank, 2017). This is an indication that customary or indigenous regime governs land and resources access for more than 2 billion people around the world today and the risk include perpetrating and aggravating conflict and violence, poverty and marginalization of the vulnerable among others. (Freudenberger, 2016)

The Prevailing conventional method of Land titling and registration in Nigeria since 1883 has left much to be desired due to its inability to meet the challenges of providing formal title to majority of land owners (Oluwadare and Kufoniyi, 2015) Currently, only 3% of the total land area of 923,768 square kilometer has been registered (PTCLR, 2016; Nwilo, 2018). Under the conventional method, it takes about 62 days to register a Certificate of Occupancy (C of O) without survey-related problem, 17 procedures and cost 24% of the property value in Oyo state (World Bank, 2011).

Unregistered Land makes the holder lack legal means of protecting their rights to land from competing claims of others (Holland, Masuda and Robinson, 2022). Unregistered land rights also affect land transaction. For instance, an important influence on farmer's inclination to embark on large scale farming investment is their security of tenure. These and other economic predicament faced by nations as a result of inadequate or inaccurate land records is enormous and this had prompted government of Nations across the world to intervene through a system of land administration in which land titles are issued as a way of subjugating this economic woe face by the poor. (Oluwadare and Kufoniyi, 2015). Some of indices of measuring performance in relation to land titling and registration system are procedure, time and cost (World Bank, 2014; Chen, 2013)

The major problems of manual filing and card system in Land registration system in Nigeria have been identified as time delay and high cost of registration. Land title registration is beclouded with delay due to many stages and bureaucratic processes involved. Bogarets and Zevenbergen (2001) while advocating for general boundaries argued that demarcating, measuring and registration of fixed boundaries require more time and efforts. Also World Bank study on Africa shows that if no dispute occurs, the process of land registration takes an average of 15-18 months and normally, a period of 2-7 years is not uncommon (UNCHS, 1991).

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study aims compare the conventional and certificate of occupancy redefined methods of land title registration in Oyo State. The purpose is to find out how this new method (C of O redefined) functions in contrast to the conventional approach. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the cost of obtaining a Certificate of Occupancy under both methods in the

- study area;
- ii. Investigate the procedure involved in both methods and;
- iii. Examine the turnaround time for completing a Certificate of Occupancy under the two methods;

1.3 The Study Area

The study area covers Ibadan region, Oyo State. This area covers a land area of approximately 8669.418 km² which constitute 22.18% of Oyo State total land area of 39,077.69 km². Ibadan region is bounded in the North by Afijio Local Government, in the East by Osun and Ogun State in the south by Ogun State and in the West by Ibarapa East Local Government and Ogun State. (Figure 1.1) The entire Oyo state is homogenous and comprises of the Oyos, the Ibadans, and the Ibarapas all belonging to Yoruba family and speaking the same Yoruba language, the economy of Oyo State is based chiefly on agriculture and handicrafts. Industries in Ibadan, the second largest city in Nigeria includes cannery, brewery and publishing industry among others.

Figure 1.1: Map of the Study Area

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Map-of-Ibadan-showing-major-communities_fig1_338568390

1.4 Materials and Methods

1.4.1 Research Design

In order to achieve the research objectives and to answer the research questions a case study research design was applied. A case study research design is also suitable for a research whose object is to evaluate impact or effectiveness of a programme or policy (Mukarage, 2016). As the study aims to assess the performance of Land Title Registration project in terms of procedure, time and cost, a case study approach is found to be appropriate.

1.5 Types and Source Data

Both primary and secondary data were sourced and used for the study. Primary data were sourced from the beneficiaries of Certificate of Occupancy redefined government intervention. Information sought includes their opinion on Efficiency of the new method compared to the conventional approach in term of time, cost and procedure. Secondary data were collected from relevant offices in the Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development. Information such as the procedure, cost and time for completing registration of Certificate of Occupancy were collected.

1.6 Data Collection Method

A cross-sectional study of questionnaire survey research design approach was adopted based on the previous work of Klein (2003); therefore, a drop-off and pick procedure of data collection was applied in this regard. In-depth interview, Focus group discussion and mobile data collection methods were used to collect information from the beneficiaries. The data was subjected to data cleansing and data cleaning in order to identify the missing value, sample characteristics and meet the assumptions of normality. Equally, the variables were subjected to validity test. The validity of the instrument in this study was measured via Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (Muhammad, 2009).

1.7 Data Analysis Techniques

The descriptive and inferential statistical analyses were utilized in this study. These involved frequency, percentage, table, figure, and Chi-square analysis, respectively. Descriptive analysis was utilized to summarize the profile of the participants. Chi-square was equally employed to test the research hypothesis.

1.8 Results and Discussion of Findings

The study showed that registration takes place after all requirements have been met. The

deed registry where registration takes place is divided into different units. Each unit has a specific role to play during the course of registration of an instrument. Instruments relating to land that owners desire to be legally preserved are registered under a simple guideline outlined in the land instrument registration law cap 56 of 1935 in Oyo State (Prior and Prior Associate Ltd., 1992).

Document for registration is presented at the document admission counter to the Assistant Deed Registrar (ADR) who compares and check the original with copies and ensure that they are not different. After that he places upon it a stamp that indicate that the instrument has been presented and will be requested to pay to the revenue collector the sum of N30,000 or N40,000 depending on the location of the land. However, this amount is renewable from time to time. After payment of necessary fee the whole set of the instrument that is, original, counterpart and Registry copy is returned to registration process and the document forwarded to the office of Higher Deed Registrar (HDR) who thoroughly check all copies presented and ensure that they are identical, correct and compliance with registration regulations and registerable before appending his signature which indicate that the instrument is accepted for registration. On the other hand, if the document is found to be defective the HDR will raise a query and the presenter will be requested to amend and represent or the instrument may be refused out rightly by endorsing on the instrument and copy "Registration Refused" in red ink. After it has been accepted for registration, the HDR passes the document to the plan Record/Card keeping unit for proper charting of the survey plan by the surveyor attached to Deed Registry in the published/cadastral sheets to determine whether the property is free of encroachment and also to update the record on latest transaction on the property. If the property does not encroach on another man's property, the surveyor will endorse the document and document will be given a card number (and the number will be recorded at the back page of the instrument and also be indicated in the published sheets) which can bear the name of the owner and location of the property and kept along with others in the appropriate docket in the plan record room (for ease of identification the number may carry the nomenclature New, Old and C of O (Tables 1.1, and 1.3).

Thereafter, the instrument passes to the Registration unit where Deed Registrar duly register the instrument in a register that has been opened for such instrument and a designated serial number, page and volume will be given. Each type of instrument is classified into different volume that is, volume containing certificate of occupancy will be separated from any other type of document and each volume normally contains sixty (60) documents arranged serially.

A register for sublease is usually provided for each local government and quasi-governmental organizations. After registration, the instrument is forwarded to the indexing room where the document is indexed for ease of reference of registration particulars in the future. At the indexing room two types of records are kept the first is an index card where the particulars of the registered documents are recorded legibly and the cards are filed by the name of the grantor and grantee in alphabetical order. The second is a property card created for each parcel which refers to the property by a short location description. Any further document registered concerning that parcel is recorded against the card. These cards are kept in the appropriate docket. After the indexing the instrument is passed to the principal Deed Registrar (PDR) for his final signature. Then the document is sent to the charting room to record the registration particulars in the card that was open first and finally move to the counter where final entries are recorded and the instrument delivered to the presenter. After collection the certified true copy (CTC) will be filed in appropriate volume and the volume dispatched to the strong room for safe keeping.

Table 1.1: Designation and Activities of Process Chart under Homeowner and C of O Redefined

	Designation	Activities
1	Land Registry / LUD Registry	Registration of tiles
2	Director of Lands Deputy Director Lands Assistant Deputy Director Lands Officer in Charge at C of O room	Vetting of particulars in the file
3	Advertisement Section/ Room	For advertisement in the Dailies (wait for 21 days for any adverse claim(s) on the Land)
4	Zonal Land Office (ZLO)	Physical inspection of the land
5	Advertisement Section/Room	To examine the Reports of the ZLO
6	Officer in Charge at C of O room Assistant Deputy Director Lands Deputy Director Lands Director Lands Permanent Secretary	Vetting of the ZLO Reports vis-a-vis the particulars in the file

7	Deputy Surveyor General Surveyor General	Vetting of the File
8	Officer in Charge at C of O Room Plan Record Keeping (PRK)	Verification of the Survey plan / lodging of a copy
9	Officer in charge at C of O Room	Payment of Charting Fees, Verification of the payments: Ground Rent Deeds Preparation Fees Capital Gain Tax
10	Board of Internal Revenue	Verification of the payments already made
11	Commissioner for Lands	To append his signature or comments
12	Stamp Duties	Stamping
13	Deeds Registry	For Final Registration
14	The Counter	For Registration and Collection
15	Room 4 & 5	Application form & submission

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2022

Table 1.2: Stages, Items of Cost and Turnaround Time for Completion of Document under Conventional Method

Title	Stage	Element of Cost (Items)	Time
Certificate of Occupancy	1. Application and Opening of File 2. Vetting of particular of the file 3. Advertisement for 21 days for any adverse claim(s) on the land 4. Zonal land office (ZLO) for physical inspection of the site 5. Advertisement room to examine the reports. 6. C of O Room, DDL, ADL, and Director of land to vet ZLO Reports 7. Asst. & Deputy Sur. Gen to vet the file. 8. C of O RM plan record keeping (PRK) verification of the survey plan logment of a copy. 9. C of O Room payment of charting fee and verification payments.	Application fee of N5000 is subjected to a review. submission fee N10,000 Inspection N2,500 Deed preparation N10,000 Deed Registration N20,000 Ground rent depends on use: i. Residential N7.50/m ² ii. Commercial N10/m ² iii. Agricultural N1,000/hethre	Minimum of 12months if there is no survey problem

Table 1.2: Stages, Items of Cost and Turnaround Time for Completion of Document under Conventional Method

	<p>i. Groundrent</p> <p>ii. Deed preparation fee</p> <p>iii. Capital gain tax</p> <p>10. Deed Preparation</p> <p>11. Stamp Duty</p> <p>12. Deed registration and collection</p>		
<p>2. Deed of Assignment</p>	<p>1. Application</p> <p>2. Inspection to value the property by the lands officer.</p> <p>3. Approval of value</p> <p>4. Verification</p> <p>5. Preparation of consent letter</p> <p>6. Signing of consent</p> <p>7. Stamp duty</p> <p>8. Registration</p>	<p>Application N10,000</p> <p>Inspection N10,000</p> <p>Consent: Formally 10% of property value but has been reduced to 6%.</p> <p>Capital gain tax: Formally 5% of property value but has been reduced to 2%.</p> <p>Stamp duty formally 3% of property value but has been reduced to 1%.</p> <p>Registration depends on location.</p> <p>i. GRA:- N40,000</p> <p>ii. Private:- N30,000</p>	<p>2 months.</p>

3. Deed of Legal mortgage	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Application 2. Preparation of consent 3. Verification of fees 4. Signing of consent 5. Stamp duty 6. Registration 	<p>Application fee N10,000</p> <p>Consent fee 2% of Loan</p> <p>Stamp duty 0.06 x rent x unexpired term.</p> <p>Registration N30,000</p>	1 Month
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Source: Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development (2022)

Table 1.3: Title Registration Stages, Items of Costs and Turnaround time for Completion under Home Owner & Certificate of Occupancy Redefined Approach

Title	Stage	Element of Cost (Items)	Time
1. Certificate of Occupancy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.) Application form Room 4 2.) Submission of document Room 5. 3.) Advert for 21 days for any adverse claim on the land. 4.) 7 days after advert for 21 days physical inspection of the site by town planning office lands officer and surveyor-ZLO office. 5.) Vetting the reports of ZLO 6.) Manual charting (charting 1) 7.) Hon. Commissioner for comments Directors of lands Deputy Director and C of O Room. 8.) Board of internal revenue to verify all payments. 	<p>Application fee N10,000</p> <p>Survey verifications N5,000</p> <p>Cost of Registration depends on use:</p> <p>Agricultural Land</p> <p>0-5 acres – N200,000</p> <p>5.1-10 acres – N300,000</p> <p>10.1-20 acres–N350,000</p> <p>20.1- 50 acres-N600,000</p> <p>50 & above acres-N750,000</p> <p>Residential land Use</p> <p>Virgin land – N150,000</p> <p>Bungalow – N170,000</p> <p>1.5 Storey Bulding N200,000</p> <p>2 & Above storey Building N220,000</p> <p>Residential/Commercial N400,000</p>	60 days after Advert

	<p>9.) Deed Registry and charting 10.) Deed Registry to obtain registration particular. 11.) Consultancy for C of O printing. 12.) Hon. Commissioner for signature 13.) PS, Director of Land. 14.) Deed Registry for Signature and collection</p>	<p>Commercial Land Small scale 1000m - 2500m N250,000 Medium Scale 2500m²- 4000m²- N300,000 Large Scale 4000m²- 10,000- N350,000 Schools, Private Cemetery, Hospital etc – N400,000 Petrol Station, Gas Plant Warehouse & Event Centre – N550,000</p>	<p>60 days after Advert</p>
<p>2. Deed of Assignment</p>	<p>1.) Application 2.) Inspection to value the property by the lands officer. 3.) Approval of value 4.) Verification 5.) Preparation of consent letter 6.) Signing of consent 7.) Stamp duty 8.) Registration</p>	<p>Application N10,000 Inspection N10,000 Consent: Formally 10% of property value but has been reduced to 6%. Capital gain tax: Formally 5% of property value but has been reduced to 2%. Stamp duty formally 3% of property value but has been reduced to 1%. Registration depends on location. i. GRA:- N40,000 ii. Private:- N30,000</p>	<p>2 months.</p>

3. Deed of Legal mortgage	1.) Application 2.) Preparation of consent 3.) Verification of fees 4.) Signing of consent 5.) Stamp duty 6.) Registration	Application fee N10,000 Consent fee 2% Loan Stamp duty 0.06 x rent x unexpired term. Registration N30,000	1 month
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Source: Ministry of Lands, Housing and Urban Development (2022)

Table 1.4: Tabulation of Results obtained from Beneficiaries' Response in terms of Efficiency of Time, Procedure and Cost

Perception of Beneficiaries about Cost, Time and Procedure of Registration	Legend: SD – Strongly Agree D – Disagree A – Agree SA – Strongly Agree						
	SD	D	A	SA	M	SD	(x ² /P-Value)
1) Regularization method is more efficient than Conventional method in terms of cost	164	0	359	277	3.11	1.079	311.83 (0.000)
2) Regularization method is more efficient than conventional method in terms of procedure	100	126	161	413	2.50	1.257	291.27 (0.000)

3) Regularization method is less efficient than conventional method in terms of time	320	178	139	361	2.11	1.056	157.99 (0.000)
4) Regularization method is not affordable	387	150	56	207	3.14	0.729	71.90 (0.000)
5) Regularization procedure is not efficient	122	178	139	361	2.92	1.131	181.05 (0.000)
Source: Authors' Analysis, 2022							

Table 1.5: Result of Chi-square Test on Hypothesis Testing

	Procedure, Time and Cost
Chi-Square	359.920 ^a
Df	11
Asymp. Sig	.000
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 66.7	

Source: Field Survey

The hypothesis being tested in Table 1.5 is that regularization method (Certificate of Occupancy redefined) was not significantly efficient in terms of procedure, time and cost. The analysis showed a Chi-square value of 359.920 with 11 degree of freedom and asymptotic significant level of 0.000 which indicated that there was a significant association between and its efficiency in terms of procedure, time and cost. The fact that there were no cells with expected frequencies less than 5 and the minimum expected cell frequency is 66.7 suggests that the sample size was large enough to support the statistical analysis. Also, the p-value of 0.000 was less than the chosen level of significance 0.005. Based on these results, we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is evidence to suggest that C of O redefined method is significantly efficient in terms of procedure, time and cost.

1.9 Conclusion

This study revealed that while conventional approach starts from lands registry, the Home owners and certificate of occupancy redefined starts from room 4 where application form is obtainable and paid for. There, computer is used to aid the process. The number of stages involved in both conventional and Homeowner and certificate of occupancy redefined are almost the same, the only difference is that conventional approach made use of files and card systems while Home owners and certificate of occupancy redefined method uses information and computer technology in some of the stages (ICT). This tends to slow down the rate at which tasks are accomplished under conventional approach and it takes almost a year to process certificate of occupying (World Bank, 2011). However some of the operations in Home owners and certificate of occupancy redefined are computer oriented e.g. charting (2) Room 4, where filed is open for applicants etc. this tends to speed up the process such that the whole process of obtaining C of O is completed in 60 day except for those that have survey related problems.

Administrative requirements for each approach is explained in Tables 1 and 2 and stages and items of cost and turnaround time for completing each transaction is also explained in table 1 & 2 for comparative analysis process charts are also provided to explain the movement of documents for processing certificate of occupancy under conventional and Home owner and certificate of occupancy redefined in Oyo State. All payments are inclusive under Certificate of Occupancies of redefined method while in conventional approach there are different payments during the process.

This study concludes that Homeowner and Certificate of Occupancy redefined approach in Oyo State is a paradigm shift at facilitating effective and efficient land registration in Nigeria in general and Oyo State in particular as opposed to the prevailing conventional approach which is adjudged slow, cumbersome, costly and not transparent (PTCLR, 2016). It is also advised that in the area of capacity building, staff members should be adequately equipped to improve the process of title registration, similarly survey staff should be trained in the ways of modern survey equipment such as orthophotos intelligent scanning machines, personal computer and internet facilities among others.

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